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ANTI-CORROSION AND ANTIBACTERIAL TESTS OF QUATERNARY SALTS BASED ON PYRIDINE-CONTAINING AMIDES AND UREAS

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Abstract

The tests have shown that the synthesized salts [1] 3-(N-1-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride, 3-(N-2-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride, 3-(N-2-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-allylpyridinium bromide and 3-(N-(3-quinolyl-N-benzylquinolilium chloride carboxamido)pyridyl)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride exhibit significant anti-corrosion activity compared to the industrial inhibitor KI-1.

3-(N-phenylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride, 3-(N-1-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride and 3-(N-2-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride were investigated for antibacterial and fungicidal activity.

The Firefly software package was used to calculate the most energetically favorable conformations for the compounds 3-(N-phenylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride, 3-(N-1-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride, 3-(N-2-naphthylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chloride, and 3-(N-(2-pyridyl)carboxamido)pyridyl-N,N-dibenzylpyridinium chloride, 3-(N-(4-pyridyl)carboxamido)pyridyl-N,N-dibenzylpyridinium chloride, and 3-(N-(3-quinolyl-N-benzylquinolilium chloride)carboxamido)pyridyl-N-benzylpyridinium chloride. It is shown that compounds with the highest anti-corrosion ability have a more planar fragment, as a result of which the protected metal surface increases. For these same compounds, the calculation of the energies of the VZMO and HVMO, as well as their dipole moments, was carried out. A correlation was established between the corrosion inhibition coefficient γ and the energy difference ΔE and their derivative ΔN (the fraction of electrons transferred). An exponential form of these correlations was proposed.

Keywords: corrosion inhibitors, quaternary ammonium salts, N-arylnicotinamides, quaternized and diquaternized salts, quaternized salts based on nicotine-containing ureas.

Materials and methods

Corrosion tests of salts in 3M hydrochloric acid were carried out by the massometric method, using steel samples of 08 kp and using 3 g·l⁻¹ of synthesized salts for inhibition. The duration of the tests at 40°C was 2 h, at 60°C – 1 h and at 80°C – 0.25 h. The results of the experiments are presented in the corresponding tables.

Some synthesized salts were tested for possible antibacterial and fungicidal effects against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) and *Candida* (*C. albicans*). The test results were compared with the most effective pyridinium salt, 4-(2-(2-methylbenzylidenehydrazyl)-1-(3-phenylpropyl)pyridinium bromide, previously studied, and ceftazidime, a pharmacological drug with a broad spectrum of antibacterial activity. The results of the studies are presented in Table 7.

Results and discussion.

The method of anti-corrosion protection of metals, based on the use of corrosion inhibitors, i.e. chemical

compounds, "which, being present in the system in sufficient concentration, reduce the rate of corrosion of metals", has been known for many centuries [3]. However, only in the middle of the twentieth century, scientific ideas about the mechanism of action of inhibitors were formed, and then the first successes in their synthesis appeared. The search for such a method is due to the great damage caused by corrosion, not only in technological or economic terms [4]. No less dangerous is the deterioration of the environmental situation caused by the ingress of corrosion products into the environment [5] or toxic reagents that are formed as a result of corrosion of chemical production equipment and pipelines [6]. Considering that in industrially developed countries, damage from metal corrosion exceeds 5% of the national product, one of the main methods of combating it - the creation and use of inhibitors - should be considered as an urgent scientific and technical task.

The action of inhibitors is associated with a change in the state of the protective surface due to adsorption or formation of poorly soluble compounds with metal cations, which reduce the area of the active

surface of the metal. The modern classification consists of oxidizers, inhibitors of adsorption, complexing and polymer types [7]. Such a division indicates the diversity of the mechanisms of action of inhibitors and the possibility of using the achievements of various fields of chemistry for protection against corrosion. Among inhibitors, an important place is occupied by organic compounds that are capable of forming with cations of the metal being protected, poorly soluble in water compounds [2, 8-10]. As a result of their interaction with the surface, ultrathin (thickness ≤ 10 nm) protective films are often formed, resistant to the effects of the corrosive environment (humid atmosphere, aqueous solutions of salts and even some acids).

In the review [12], the ability of one of the nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds, pyridine, to form complex compounds on the surfaces of some metals in aqueous solutions was noted. However, the effectiveness of corrosion protection using pyridine is noticeably lower than when using its derivatives containing additional amino groups, for example, in position 2 or 4. It was assumed that if there is a second reaction center in the inhibitor molecule, under certain conditions it is possible to form chelate cycles with metal cations, which significantly increases the stability of the protective layer on the surface. This possibility can be realized during the polymerization of a heterocyclic base, such as polyvinylpyridine. The strengthening of the bond with the metal is achieved not only due to the bond with the heteroatom, but also due to the π -electron interaction of the aromatic nucleus with the surface, which has often been explained by the ability of quinoline and its derivatives to form a thin, sparingly soluble film of a complex with the metal, which protects iron, copper and zinc in aqueous solutions at $\text{pH} \geq 5.0$. The protection of copper by polycyclic N-containing heterocycles has been explained in a similar way [13].

Many works are devoted to the experimental study of heterocyclic inhibitors [11, 14-17]. On the other hand, many theoretical studies are presented to determine the relationship between structural and electronic parameters and the corrosion inhibition efficiency [18, 19].

The HOMO and LUMO frontier orbitals of chemical compounds are very important in determining their ability to inhibit corrosion. Previously, a correlation was found between the corrosion rate (or the efficiency of its inhibition) and the E_{HOMO} energy, which is often associated with the electron-donating ability of the molecule. A review of the literature shows that the adsorption of an inhibitor on a metal surface can occur on the basis of donor-acceptor interactions between the π -electrons of heterocyclic compounds and vacant d-orbitals of metal surface atoms [86]. A high E_{HOMO} value of a molecule indicates its ability to donate electrons to a corresponding acceptor molecule with low energy of free molecular orbitals. An increase in the E_{HOMO} value promotes adsorption, and, consequently, an increase in the efficiency of corrosion inhibition, affecting the process of electron transfer through the adsorbed layer. Similar relationships have been found between the corrosion rate and the difference between these two energies (the energy "gap"): $\Delta E = E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$ [20-22].

The HOMO energy indicates the ability of a molecule to accept electrons. The lower the E_{LUMO} value, the more likely it is that the molecule will accept electrons. Therefore, a large value of ΔE will give a low inhibitory capacity and vice versa – a decrease in the value of ΔE contributes to the effectiveness of corrosion inhibition [23]. Thus, a correlation was found for some piperidine derivatives [24], benzothiazoles, pyrimidines, quinolines [25], pyrazolepyrimidines [26], and pyridines [27].

Another way to relate the inhibition efficiency to the molecular structure parameters is to calculate the fraction of electrons transferred from the inhibitor to the metal surface. The E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} of the inhibitor molecule are related to the ionization potential (I) and electron affinity (A), respectively [95]. The ionization potential and electron affinity are defined as $I = -E_{\text{HOMO}}$ and $A = -E_{\text{LUMO}}$, respectively. Then the absolute electronegativity (χ) and absolute rigidity (η) of the inhibitor molecule are approximated as follows [23]:

$$\chi = \frac{I + A}{2}$$

$$\eta = \frac{I - A}{2}$$

The softness of an inhibitor molecule is expressed through the inverse stiffness:

$$S = \frac{1}{\eta}$$

The softness of an inhibitor molecule is expressed through the inverse stiffness:

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta}, \text{ де } \mu - \text{ дипольний момент.}$$

By definition, this measure measures the tendency of a chemical to accept electrons. A more reactive nucleophile is characterized by a lower μ , ω value; conversely, a good electrophile is characterized by a higher μ , ω value. Absolute electrophilicity measures the stabilization energy when the system acquires an additional electron charge ΔN from the environment. Thus, the fraction of electrons transferred from the inhibitor to the metal surface, ΔN , is given by [27]:

$$\Delta N = \frac{\chi_{\text{Fe}} - \chi_{\text{inh}}}{2(\eta_{\text{Fe}} + \eta_{\text{inh}})}$$

where χ_{Fe} and χ_{inh} are the absolute electronegativity of iron and the inhibitor molecule, respectively; η_{Fe} and η_{inh} are the absolute rigidity of iron and the inhibitor molecule, respectively. In order to calculate the fraction of electrons transferred, the theoretical value $\chi_{\text{Fe}} = 7.0$ eV [27] and $\eta_{\text{Fe}} = 0$ are used, assuming that for the metal mass $I = A$ [28]. The graphs of the dependences of the corrosion rate and the degree of corrosion protection on the fraction of electrons transferred are presented in Fig. 1.6.5 and Fig. 1.6.6, respectively [27]. Значення ΔN показує перенесення електронів від молекули до поверхні металу, якщо $\Delta N > 0$ і навпаки, якщо $\Delta N < 0$ [98, 99]. Ефективність

гальмування корозії зростає із збільшенням донорної здатності молекули на металевій поверхні, якщо $\Delta N < 3,6$.

Anti-corrosion tests of quaternized amide salts.

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, when going from nicotinamide **15** to N-arylnicotinamides **9-11**, their anticorrosive properties increase, especially for N-naphthylamides **10** and **11**. This dependence can be associated only with a change in the structure of the amide group, since the protonated pyridine fragment in all these amides is the same. In this regard, it can be assumed that the corrosion rate decreases both due to the adsorption of amide groups on the metal surface and due to their ability to form polymeric complexes with Fe(II) as a corrosion product [29]. Calculation [30, 31] of the geometric parameters of the most energetically favorable conformations of N-arylnicotinamides **9-11** shows that their structure remains close to the planar one from **9** to **11**, and the amide group is sterically accessible enough to create surface complexes of the chemisorbing type. This is evident from the decrease in corrosion rate with increasing temperature, for example, in the presence of amides **10** and **11**. Amide **9** probably forms unstable surface complexes due to the freer rotation of the phenyl radical around the C-N bond [32],

while the adsorption-blocking effect and the size of the naphthyl radicals contribute to the formation of stronger complexes and, accordingly, increase the protection of the metal surface. The best test results were obtained from compounds **13** and **14**, for which the corrosion inhibition coefficient γ at 80°C is 766 and 733, respectively [33]. For comparison, it should be noted that for the industrial inhibitor KI-1 this coefficient is 252.5 at the same temperature.

Quaternization of N-arylnicotinamides **9-11** with benzyl chloride allows creating in their structure another adsorption center – quaternary ammonium cation, which affects the electrode processes due to electrostatic adsorption [34]. The benzyl fragment in the obtained salts **12-14**, as shown by calculations of their geometric parameters [30, 31], is located above the plane of the pyridine ring and does not interfere with the adsorption of the corresponding ammonium cation on the metal surface. As in the case of amides **9-11**, the size and less free rotation of naphthyl radicals around the C-N bond in salts **13** and **14** probably contribute to the formation of stronger complexes of the chemisorbing type on the metal surface than for salt **12**, obtained on the basis of N-phenylnicotinamide **9**. This leads to a significant decrease in the corrosion rate and an increase in the degree of metal protection (see Table 1).

Table 1.

Effect of N-arylnicotinamides **9-11** and 3-(N-arylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chlorides **12-14** on the corrosion of 08 kp steel in 3M hydrochloric acid

Compound	40°C		60°C		80°C	
	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %
<p style="text-align: center;">9</p>	4.2	76.2	3.5	71.4	3.9	74.4
<p style="text-align: center;">10</p>	155.5	99.3	313.1	99.6	223.1	99.5
<p style="text-align: center;">11</p>	115.5	99.1	220.4	99.5	362.5	99.7

<p style="text-align: center;">12</p>	19.9	95.0	12.6	92.1	9.7	89.7
<p style="text-align: center;">13</p>	224.0	99.5	446.0	99.8	766.0	99.9
<p style="text-align: center;">14</p>	192.5	99.5	420.0	99.8	733.0	99.9
<p style="text-align: center;">15</p>	3.5	71.4	2.4	58.3	2.3	56.5

To assess the anticorrosive properties of N-allylpyridinium halides, their effect on the corrosion of 08 kp steel in 3M hydrochloric acid at 40-80°C was studied, determining the corrosion inhibition coefficient γ and the degree of corrosion protection Z. The results of the experiments for a number of the most corrosion-retarding salts are given in Table 2, from which it follows that the more effective inhibitors are salts based on N-aryl nicotinamides (**17**, **18** and **20**). Among them, compound **17** is of interest, for which the corrosion inhibition coefficient γ increases to 354.6 when the temperature rises to 80°C. Such an increase in the protective effect in salt **17** can be explained by the effect

of chemisorption of the naphthyl radical on the metal surface, since its rotation around the C-N bond is complicated in comparison with the rotation of the phenyl radical in compounds **18** and **20**. This confirms the calculation of the geometric parameters of energetically favorable conformations of salts (**17**, **18**, and **20**), given by the method proposed in [30] and shows that the main fragment of the structure of salt **17** is closer to planar than that of salts **18** and **20**. A similar pattern is observed for 3-(N-arylcarboxamido)-N-benzylpyridinium chlorides [35, 36].

Table 2.
Effect of substituted N-allylpyridine halides on corrosion of 08 kp steel in 3M hydrochloric acid

Compound	40°C		60°C		80°C	
	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %
 17	120.3	99.2	15.3	99.5	354.6	99.7
 18	93.7	98.9	78.3	98.7	64.5	98.5
 20	165.0	99.4	159.6	99.4	145.6	99.3
 21	64.5	98.5	84.6	98.8	100.3	99.0

The results of anti-corrosion tests of diquaternized amides are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.Effect of diquaternized amides **28-30** on corrosion of 08 kp steel in 3M hydrochloric acid

Compound	40°C		60°C		80°C	
	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %
<p style="text-align: center;">28</p>	44.0	97.7	56.3	98.2	65.3	98.5
<p style="text-align: center;">29</p>	133.5	99.3	197.5	99.5	228.9	99.6
<p style="text-align: center;">30</p>	113.9	99.1	206.7	99.5	326.2	99.7

As can be seen from the table, when going from salt **28** to **30**, their anti-corrosion properties increase. It can be assumed that the conformation of the molecules during this transition changes in such a way that it contributes to maximum protection of the metal surface. This is confirmed by the corresponding calculations.

It should also be noted that compound **30**, the best performing of the salts presented here, outperforms the industrial inhibitor KI-1 by a factor of 1.3.

Anti-corrosion tests of quaternary urea-based salts.

As can be seen from the data in Table 4, the indicated salts exhibit moderate anti-corrosion activity. This is due to the free rotation of the phenyl radical around the C-N bond, which creates a small area for protecting the metal surface.

Table 4.Effect of salts **33** and **34** on the corrosion of 08 kp steel in 3M hydrochloric acid.

Compound	40°C		60°C		80°C	
	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %	γ	Z, %
 33	65.3	98.5	89.5	98.5	130.5	99.2
 34	62.1	98.4	89.5	98.5	163.1	99.4

Calculation of conformations of synthesized quaternary salts.

The calculation was performed using the Firefly (formerly known as PC GAMESS) B3LYP/6-31G* software package, which allows finding the conformation with the minimum energy, determining the

HOMO and LUMO energies, and the charges of chemisorption centers. Thus, quaternary salts **12-14** (monoquaternized) and **28-30** (di-quaternized) were calculated. The figures below show the most energetically favorable conformations for these compounds.

Fig. 1. The most favorable conformation of compound 12

Fig. 2. The most favorable conformation of compound 13

Fig. 3. The most favorable conformation of compound 14

Fig. 4. The most favorable conformation of compound 28

Fig. 5. The most favorable conformation of compound 29

Fig. 6. The most favorable conformation of compound 30

As can be seen from the figures, monoquaternized salts have a structure close to planar, which allows them to cover a larger area of the metal surface, while the conformational arrangement of diquaternized salts does not allow two centers to be equally fixed on the metal surface and work simultaneously.

Calculations showed that the charges on the nitrogen atoms of different compounds are almost the same and are on average: for pyridinium nitrogen - -

0.926, for amide nitrogen - -1.069, for pyridine (quinoline) nitrogen of diquaternized compounds - - 0.977. As can be seen, the charge of amide nitrogen is also a sorption center and can participate in fixing the molecule on the metal surface.

The program also determined the HOMO and LUMO energies, the indicators of which are presented in table 5.

Table 5.

Results of calculations of MO energies of synthesized salts

Compound	Corrosion inhibition coefficient		Energy of MO, eV		$\Delta E = E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}$, eV
	γ (80°C)	$[\gamma]$	HOMO	LUMO	
<p>12</p>	9.7	0.33	-11.0	-2.52	8.48
<p>13</p>	766	22.57	-10.13	-2.49	7.64

<p style="text-align: center;">14</p>	733	21.6	-9.89	-2.5	7.39
<p style="text-align: center;">28</p>	65.3	1.71	-14.19	-4.84	9.35
<p style="text-align: center;">29</p>	228.9	6.0	-13.96	-4.77	9.19
<p style="text-align: center;">30</p>	326.2	7.56	-14.33	-5.17	9.16

Previously, a correlation was found between the corrosion inhibition efficiency and the difference in LUMO and HOMO energies [27], therefore, based on

these calculations, a graph of the dependence of the reduced value of the corrosion inhibition coefficient on the energy difference $[\gamma] = f(\Delta E)$ was constructed and an approximation was performed ($K_{cor} = 0.96$).

Fig. 7. Correlation between energy differences ΔE and corrosion inhibition coefficients $[\gamma]$ of diquaternized 28 (1), 29 (2), 30 (3) and monoquaternized 14 (4), 13 (5) amides.

As follows from the works [37, 38, 39], the dependence of the parameters characterizing the effectiveness of the inhibitor (corrosion rate and corrosion current density) is exponential. Therefore, ΔE was introduced into a power, a graph of the dependence $[\gamma] = f(e\Delta E)$ was constructed and an equation of the form was derived:

$$[\gamma] = k \cdot e^{\Delta E} + C,$$

where $k = -2.03 \cdot 10^{-5}$; $C = 2.6$; $[\gamma]$ is the reduced value of the corrosion inhibition coefficient and is equal to:

$$[\gamma] = \frac{\gamma}{M}, \quad M - \text{the molar mass of the compound.}$$

Fig. 8. Exponential correlation between energy differences ΔE and corrosion inhibition coefficients $[\gamma]$ of diquaternized 28 (1), 29 (2), 30 (3) and monoquaternized 14 (4), 13 (5) amides.

Fig. 9. Correlation between the fractions of electrons transferred, ΔN , and the corrosion inhibition coefficients $[\gamma]$ of diquaternized **28** (1), **29** (2), **30** (3) and monoquaternized **14** (4), **13** (5) amides.

Fig. 10. Exponential correlation between the fractions of electrons transferred, ΔN , and the corrosion inhibition coefficients $[\gamma]$ of diquaternized **28** (1), **29** (2), **30** (3) and monoquaternized **14** (4), **13** (5) amides..

So, as can be seen from all the graphs, when introducing the exponential dependence, the correlation coefficient has significantly improved compared to the corresponding dependencies given in [27], for which Kcor is 71-93%.

Table 6 presents the calculated quantum-chemical parameters, such as HOMO (EHOMO) and LUMO

(ELUMO) energies, their energy difference (ΔE), dipole moment (μ), ionization potential (I), electron affinity (A), absolute electronegativity (χ), global rigidity (η), electrophilicity (ω), softness (S), electron transfer fraction (ΔN), and degree of corrosion protection (Z), for the most and least effective compounds as corrosion inhibitors.

Table 6.

Quantum-chemical parameters for compounds **14** and **28**

Parameter	Compound 14	Compound 28
E_{HOMO} , eB	-9.89	-14.19
E_{LUMO} , eB	-2.5	-4.84
$\Delta E = E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$, eB	7.39	9.35
$I = -E_{\text{HOMO}}$, eB	9.89	14.19
$A = -E_{\text{LUMO}}$, eB	2.5	4.84
χ , eB	6.195	9.515
η , eB	3.695	4.675
μ , дебай	11.83	6.083
ω	18.937	3.957
S	0.27	0.214
ΔN	1.487	-5.878
Z, %	99.9	98.5

As is known, the energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital (E_{HOMO}) indicates the ability of a molecule to donate electrons to the corresponding acceptor molecules with a low energy, empty molecular orbital. At higher values of E_{HOMO} , the molecule has a greater ability to donate electrons, its adsorption properties increase, and, consequently, the effectiveness of corrosion inhibition. Thus, Table 6 shows that compound **14** has a higher E_{HOMO} value, therefore it is more effective than compound **28**.

An important parameter of the reactivity of an inhibitor molecule with respect to adsorption on a metal surface is the difference in HOMO and LUMO energies. When the ΔE value decreases, the reactivity of the molecule increases, which leads to an increase in its efficiency as an inhibitor. In our study, compounds **14** and **28** have the smallest and largest such energy difference, respectively.

The dipole moment μ is another important parameter. A high value of the dipole moment increases the adsorption between the chemical compound and the metal surface [40]. The strain energy increases with increasing μ , which allows the molecule to adsorb more easily on the iron surface. An increase in μ indicates an increase in the volume of the inhibitor molecule, which increases the contact area between the molecule and the metal surface and enhances the corrosion inhibition ability. In our study, the μ value of compound **14** is almost twice as high as that of **28**.

Absolute stiffness and softness are important properties for measuring molecular stability and reactivity. It is obvious that chemical stiffness indicates resistance to deformation or electronic polarization. A stiff molecule has a large energy difference, a soft one has a small one. As a rule, the inhibitor with the lowest global stiffness value (and therefore with high global softness) has a high corrosion inhibition efficiency, which is observed in Table 6 for compounds **14** and **28**.

The absolute electronegativity χ describes the ability of a molecule to attract electrons to itself. According to the principle of electronegativity equalization, a molecule **28** with a high electronegativity quickly reaches

equalization and therefore has a low corrosion inhibition efficiency.

The number of transferred electrons ΔN , which shows the efficiency of corrosion inhibition as a result of electron donation, was also calculated and is given in Table 6. If $0 < \Delta N < 3.6$, the inhibitory efficiency increases due to the increase in the ability of the compounds to donate electrons to the metal surface. Thus, a high proportion of transferred electrons is associated with the better inhibitor **14**, while compound **28** has a negative ΔN value and therefore a worse efficiency.

The electrophilicity index ω indicates the ability of the inhibitor molecule to accept electrons. It is a measure of the energy stabilization of the system after accepting an additional number of electrons ΔN from the environment. In our case, compound **14** with a high electrophilicity index value (18.937) has a high inhibition efficiency compared to compound **28**, which has a low ω value (3.957).

Thus, from all the above parameters it follows that compound **14** is much more effective than compound **28**, which is consistent with the experimental data.

Monoquaternized amides as antibacterial drugs.

As is known, quaternary pyridinium halides obtained by quaternization with alkyl and aryl halides have antibacterial properties. Quaternized amine derivatives have been previously investigated for their antibacterial activity [44-47]. Therefore, some synthesized salts were investigated for possible antibacterial and fungicidal activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*), and *Candida albicans* (*C. albicans*). The test results were compared with the most effective pyridinium salt, 4-(2-(2-methylbenzylidene)hydrazyl)-1-(3-phenylpropyl)pyridinium bromide **35**, previously investigated [48], and ceftazidime **36**, a pharmacological drug with a wide spectrum of antibacterial activity. The results of the studies are presented in Table 7.

Table 7.

Antibacterial and fungicidal activity of salts

Compound	Minimum bacteriostatic concentration, mg/ml			
	E. coli	P. aeruginosa	S. aureus	C. albicans
<p style="text-align: center;">12</p>	125	125	125	125
<p style="text-align: center;">13</p>	125	125	31.25	125
<p style="text-align: center;">14</p>	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5
<p style="text-align: center;">35</p>	32	256	4	32
<p style="text-align: center;">36</p>	<0.125	1	4	-

The table shows that among the salts synthesized in this work, compound 14 exhibits the best antibacterial and fungicidal activity. Compared to ceftazidime, this salt exhibits moderate activity. It should also be noted that compound 14 has 4 times better antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) than compound 35.

Conclusions

1. A method for the synthesis of mono- and di-quaternized N-arylnicotinamides using available reagents is proposed. Preparative yields are 67-87%.

2. The tests have established that the synthesized salts 13, 14, 17 and 30 exhibit significant anticorrosion activity in comparison with the industrial inhibitor KI-1.

3. Salts **12-14** were investigated for antibacterial and fungicidal activity.

4. The most energetically favorable conformations for compounds **12-14** and **28-30** were calculated using the Firefly software package. It was shown that compounds with the highest anticorrosion activity have a more planar fragment, as a result of which the protected metal surface increases. For these same compounds, the HOMO and LUMO energies, as well as their dipole moments, were calculated. A correlation has been established between the corrosion inhibition coefficient γ and the energy difference ΔE and its derivative ΔN (the fraction of electrons transferred). An exponential form of these correlations has been proposed.

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